

Sexual Harassment, Mental Health & Job-Related Outcomes: A Case from Pakistan

Humza Mahfooz

Institute of business management(IoBM), Karachi, Pakistan

Abstract: Sexual harassment has been a growing phenomenon globally and in the last couple of decades gained lot awareness in Pakistan as well. This paper aims to understand what impact gender ratio has on sexual harassment which leads to job dissatisfaction and mental well-being of the employee. The populations selected for this quantitative research are human resource managers and working employees of from private/public organizations in Karachi. This research drafted a model where it was analysed that whether sexual harassment had an impact on task, job performance of employees and whether gender ratio moderated this relationship. The results clearly indicated that the lower proportion of women in organisations triggered sexual harassment and had a strong impact on task and job performance of employees and has a direct impact on the well-being of employees

Keywords: Sexual harassment, mental well-being, organizational diversity, job performance

I. Introduction

Background of the Research

Sexual harassment is not at all a new phenomenon, this type of gender violence has been sprouting in societies for over decades and while the description remains the same, the name has transitioned from 'Street Harassment' (Bowman, 1993), 'public harassment' (Gardner, 1995) to 'Street harassment' (Logan, 2015). Furthermore, sexual harassment does not limit itself to staring, leering, stalking but has gone beyond this point. According to a survey conducted in the streets of London, large number of women aged between 18-24 years confessed that they had been victims of sexual harassment on the streets. Moreover, a similar survey was conducted in France where around 25% women admitted that they frightened to walk on the streets all by themselves. While in the USA it was confirmed that around 65% of women had suffered sexual harassment, of which 23% had been touched in a sexual way while 20% had been stalked, 25% had been victims of verbal harassment and 9% had been asked to do a sexual favor. This signifies that sexual harassment is not just limited to certain countries, its presence is global and is happening everywhere and remains a topic that is understudied in the field of research (Adhur & Jha, 2016).

Sexual harassment has been a growing phenomenon globally and in the last couple of decades gained lot awareness in Pakistan as well. This paper aims to understand what impact gender ratio has on sexual harassment which leads to job dissatisfaction and mental well-being of the employee. The populations selected for this quantitative research are human resource managers and working employees of from private/public organizations in Karachi.

Problem Statement

Sexual harassment, gender discrimination, gender-based violence are extremely common in Pakistan's public places and most women believe that men would get away with this behavior and while others keep tolerating this intimidating behavior. Furthermore, organisation and universities are obliged legally to have inquiry committees established in order to provide safety and security to women at public places. However, these have failed and harassment continues to increase. What is much worse is the fact that a large number of cases are not even reported. In order to bring change in

Sexual Harassment, Mental Health & Job-Related Outcomes: A Case from

Pakistan, it is essential and mandatory to break the silence on sexual harassment as per Dawn news article published on 21st March, (2018).

In a recent article written by Sethna, Masood and Jahangir (2018) in Dawn news reported that 300 women sexual harassment, discrimination and sexual harassment in Pakistan's workplaces are not discussed or reported within the organization and are mostly unreported by line managers. The same study also suggests that only 17% employees report harassment at work report it to internal committees of organizations. While the organization aims to hire employees with good educational background employees still engage themselves in sexual harassment which is a serious concern for the existing employees and specially the younger generation who are finishing their education and planning to enter into the professional world.

Significance of the research

United Nations has regarded violence that particularly done based on gender differences is regarded as human rights violation. Furthermore, in a United Nations conference that was held in Vienna in the year 1993, it was stated and emphasized that sexual harassment or violence against women needs to be eradicated from all walks of life which include both public and private spaces.

Sexual harassment is no longer an old subject and has deepened its roots within the society and it is not merely limited to physical harm but it includes mental suffering as well now. Moreover, sexual harassment that was mostly under the limelight was basically that was conducted in public spaces such as schools or workplaces. However, United Nations highlighted the fact that street harassment has gained lower attention over the years and regarded it as 'under recognized global pandemic' (Adhur & Jha, 2016).

If we talk about Asian countries like Pakistan in general, it is a country that suffers from the cruelty of sexual harassment every single day, whether on streets, public spaces or at workplace. An article on Dawn newspaper published on March 21st, (2018) stated that women from diverse professions stated that unwanted comments, stalking, unwanted calling and asking for sexual favors was common in their respective professions. Furthermore, in a survey of 300 women, around 80% believed that men would get away with it. Women continue to suffer intimidation from gender-based violence and that a large number of these women choose to stay silent due to no policies or law offering them protection. This is a grave issue that needs to be addressed. Even though, in the year 2010, a law was created to eradicate sexual harassment, however women still avoid making official complains against their harasser.

Conceptual Framework

II. Literature Review

What is sexual harassment?

Sexual harassment is defined as any unwelcomed act or behavior in any organization that includes a sexual nature. (Fitzgerald, 1993). The phenomenon of sexual harassment also includes any act by manager or coworker where the person working may feel humiliated or intimidated by opposite gender. Existing research on sexual harassment has described it by identifying three main areas tripartite model: unwanted sexual attention, sexual coercion and gender harassment (Louise F. Fitzgerald, 2010)

Tripartite model sexual harassment (Fitzgerald, 1988)

Sexual coercion is also known as quid pro quo (an advantage granted in return of something) legally and psychology falls under harassment. For gender harassment it is very important to note that the sexual attention should be unwelcomed by the opposite gender, repetitive in nature and should have potential negative organizational and psychological outcomes. Finally, harassment on the basis on gender occurs when coworkers or managers discriminate or harass employees on the basis of their gender.

Theoretical background of Sexual harassment:

Scholars around the world mutually agree on the point that there is not a solo theory that explains sexual harassment. However, this research paper adopts the most common theories. These theories include natural/biological theory, sex spill over theory, organisational theory and the four-factor theory.

Ward et al. (2006) stated that these theories contain models that are used to explain the interactions and mechanism associated with each variable and that is how these theories emerge. In order to avoid over complication, the word 'theory' will be used to describe and explain sexual harassment accordingly. Furthermore, the theory appraisal criteria will be adopted which was used by Hooker (1987) and Smith (2002) in order to assist our relative appraisals. This appraisal criterion basically provides support for researchers when evaluating competing theories as stated by writers mentioned previously. Moreover, it provides scope and empirical adequacy (i.e., is the theory).

The biological/natural theory:

The biological or natural model of sexual harassments is based on an assumption that any sexual behavior in the organization should be considered discriminatory and illegitimate. However, it is believed that to be attracted to an opposite gender is a natural process and men have a higher sexual desire than woman. Another assumption believes that both genders are attracted to each other and they like to be attracted by each other in the workplace (Taylor, 1985) this model denies any assumption which leads to gender discrimination or any other kind of glass ceiling.

The biological/natural theory or model suggests that sexual harassment is an organic phenomenon which triggers from the natural attraction men and women have for each other as stated by Stockdale (1993). Furthermore, this theory also states that men are more likely to be the ones that tend to be the predator than be preyed on; this is because males are assumed to be more sex driven than women (Kinsey, Pomeroy & Martin, 1948). The highlighting feature of this theory is that men who usually harass women are usually recorded as unmarried and that harasses (victims) tend to be closer to age. Occupational status and race (Stockdale, 1993). However, according to a study conducted by Bernard (1969) states that biological theory can be viewed as misperception theory. This means that the natural sexual desire in men forces

them to look for hints in order to understand whether women are interested or not, studies suggest that these hints are more often misperceived by men.

Organizational theory

The organization model believes that sexual harassment is a way of showing superiority at workplace and often used as a means to control or intimidate employees or subordinates. Using organization power for sexual favor.

The organisational model or theory basically highlights the fact as to how power is unevenly distributed within organizations and that this power can be associated with having sexual harassment experiences (Tangri et al., 1982). Statistics show that men are more likely to harass women than the other way around. This is due to men being found to be sitting in much higher and dominating positions than women. Females tend to be found more in junior level positions or at supervisory roles. This theory suggests that it is the power factor that often leads to cases of sexual harassment than the gender of the person itself. Furthermore, it was found that men usually misperceived a woman's friendly behavior towards them regardless of the role she was in, whether it was junior role or a superior role (Johnson et al., 1991).

Socio-cultural theory

The sociocultural theory believes that sexual harassment is a part of the patriarchal society in which is dominated by men. In such society men are usually rewarded for domineering attitude and sexual aggressiveness and women of the society are suppressed and praised for their acquiescence. In such society gender roles are already pre decided and if women chose a different role by their own choice, its looked down upon.

According to Tangri, Burt and Johnson (1982) state that this socio-cultural theory presents a perspective of how the powerful abuse the powerless in the society. This statement is further elaborated and highlighted that men tend to be found in powerful positions and women are usually seen to hold positions that are of much less power and this is why women are usually harassed more than men as they are in powerless positions and thus inevitably become victims of sexual harassment. Furthermore, it was hypothesized that sexual harassment is a part and parcel of a patriarchal society; this means that gender itself is a strong variable that can be a predictor of experiences of sexual harassment and that men harass women regardless of background, age, marital status etc.

Stockdale (1993) stated that Socio cultural model/ theory basically provides a macro level perspective about sexual harassment and why is it found to be so common within the society. Moreover, a society that is patriarchal is approach, a sexually aggressive belief system is found more commonly in such societies and this belief system found in individuals tend to misperceive as stated by the theory of misperception or the natural theory.

Sex role spill over theory

This theory believes that men and women working in an organization come to their workplaces with pre-determined beliefs for example women should be hired or promoted senior positions in the organization. It usually occurs when organizations have highly skewed ratio of genders in the organization.

Sex roll spillover theory or model showcases a micro level perspective when concerned with sexual harassment. This theory highlights the fact that women and men are treated differently due to gender stereotyping beliefs that exist within the society especially when men and women are found in similar organisational roles in a business setting. This is more commonly found in situations where ratio of both genders at an organisation or workplace setting is skewed.

It has been reported that female stereotyping increases when women are found sitting at token positions within an organisation and these stereotype of females include feeling of attraction, sexiness and affection. Moreover, this theory has also suggested that women tend to be treated as properties or sex objects when there is a prominent increased ratio of women found in organizations (Stockdale, 1993). To support this idea a study conducted on women who worked in key organisational positions and that the ration of women was more, they comparatively reported more sexual harassment experiences than other organizations which were sex balanced. It should also be noted that men have this uncanny habit to misperceive cues and these misperceptions usually rise in organisations where gender is made more prominent. An example to further elaborate this idea is the way a woman may dress in an organisation, this may be led to increases sexual perceptions in comparison to an organisation where more women work (Guttek, 1985).

Sexual Harassment, Mental Health & Job-Related Outcomes: A Case from

The phenomenon of sexual harassment at workplace is centuries old. Although there is no consensus of sexual harassment, but it refers to unwanted sexual relation, verbal advances or even assault imposed at work by manager or coworker in return of a professional favor. (Siegel, 2003)

Sexual harassment is one of those subjects that are very much understudied in Asian context. Sexual Harassment is an ongoing topic and has been defined by various scholars in numerous researches. However, Sexual Harassment can be defined as any behavior that is unwelcomed by the victim, that is, physical, verbal or nonverbal (Fairchild & Rudman 2008; Hapels, Kasim, Constance & McCann, 2001). Usually flirting is often confused with sexual harassment; however, there is a highlighting difference between the two. Flirting is usually associated with common attraction between two people. Even though there is a thin line between the two, flirting does translate into harassment when it is carried out constantly without the agreement of the person who is flirted with (Brislin, 2014).

Furthermore, according to Fairchild and Rudman (2008) there are 3 basic categories which fall under the umbrella of sexual harassment. This includes harassment directed towards gender, undesired sexual attention and sexual intimidation. Gender Harassment can be described as being aggressive or hostile towards one particular gender collectively (Pina, Gannon, & Saunders, 2009). On the other hand, undesired sexual attention is defined as a humiliating or degrading behavior towards others, this is at an individual level. Examples of such a behavior may include whistling, winks, passing of sexual jokes and comments and unwanted touch (Lahsaeizadeh, & Yousefinejad, 2012). Sexual intimidation means to get sexual favors through threats or through direct/indirect requests. This research was conducted to investigate these three sexual harassment categories in Pakistan. A questionnaire was used to retrieve information from more than 500 female students.

The results demonstrated that the most frequent form of sexual harassment in Pakistan's public places were that of non-verbal (Anwar, Osterman & Bjorkqvist, 2019)

Another study conducted worked on sexual harassment that takes place in the corporate world. He highlighted that sexual harassment basically depicts inequality of power between genders and that such a problem cannot be ignored. Sexual harassment does not affect women in the corporate sector but also men. However, the former suffers more than the latter. Moreover, Pakistan is a patriarchal system which happens to be male dominated (Walby, 1990). He also stated that in such a system women are seen and treated as properties and objects, therefore experience violence. Millet (1970) pointed out that men used coercion in order to subjugate and control women.

The aim of this study is to analyze the underlying factors that stop women from reporting such cases. Some of these reasons included fear of being judged or retaliation. The study concluded that women need to be safeguarded from such incidences and this can only be done when Pakistan's political, social and economic conditions improve and status of women is protected in the society Hadi (2018).

Nicole, Isis, Ivan and Diana (2018) carried out a research on Asian American women who have been suffering from sexual harassment and stated that they have received the least attention. Statistics have suggested that in United States of America, more than half of the women who are adults are harassed in their respective workplaces. Furthermore, these women who are sexually harassed are known to develop stress disorders and worsen their psychological well-being (Ilies, Hauserman, Schwochau, & Stibal, 2003) This research has focused its efforts in conducting intersectional study on Asian American women, where the relationship between both racial harassment and sexual harassment is analyzed and the problems associated with them are highlighted in their research. The result strongly correlated with the findings of previous scholars and that a large pool of Asian American women suffered from sexual harassment. However, these behaviors were not reported or termed as Sexual Harassment.

McDonald and Charlesworth (2015) also worked around the topic of sexual harassment as well. There are abundance of researches available on sexual harassment where various dimensions have been covered, this includes the underlying causes of sexual harassment, the various problems associated with harassment, the consequences and the possible solutions of how such problems can be minimized and addressed. However, the topics that have gained lesser attention are how the same sex people are able to harass one another. Researchers such as Aggarwal and Gupta (2000) suggested that men are known to suffer from sexual harassment more than women than is assumed.

Prior studies have suggested that Pakistan is a society dominated by males and that women have spent most of their times at home, they find it difficult to interact with males at workplaces (Syed, Ali, & Winstanley, 2005). Furthermore, the occupational choices are very much limited for women in Pakistani society; this is due to lack of supportive facilities

available to them (Syed et al. 2005). The environment that surrounds Pakistan does not welcome female's employees and they are often victims of harassment and inappropriate behavior (Aasha, 2002). Furthermore, women who do join the work force are sexually harassed and the society points a finger at the women herself and men walk away with it, therefore, this makes it even more difficult for women to speak about such incidences (Ferdoos, 2005).

Another study conducted in Pakistan within the city of Lahore analyzed the relationship between sexual harassment cases of those women who use public transportations and how does this impact on the labor market for women. It was stated that when harassment cases are severe such as those

in South Asia, women tend prefer a different labor market or opt to not work at all. Moreover, the research has suggested that sexual harassment impacts women in different ways. Vera-Gray (2016) stated that women experience harassment which generally includes behaviors such as unnecessary commenting, staring, following etc. Many researchers have suggested that women are generally victims of more violence than that of men which makes them more vulnerable to sexual assault (Pain & Racheal, 1997; Stanko & Elizabeth, 1995; Madge & Clare, 1995).

This includes women who use private cars and other geographical factors were taken into consideration such as harassment cases are known to happen more at night/day or during crowded times. Furthermore, the government and policy makers aim to increase female participation in the work force. However, increased attention is not given in eradicating harassment that occurs to women who use public transportations. This research aimed at discovering how sexual harassment affects women and what effect it has on women option to work. Transportation survey data was obtained from Lahore where hypothesis was adopted and results were against the hypothesis assumed, it was analyzed that harassment cases did not have an impact on women labor market outcomes. The limitations the study faced was basically the severity could not be measure of the harassment cases and detailed information could not be gained from females (Wilder, 2018).

Sexual harassment or any conduct that is unwelcomed or unwanted; despite being given due care and attention still prevails in the organizations and has become one of the most serious concerns for employers. According to Quick and McFayden (2017) we still face sexual because of the lack of attention to the actual definition of sexual harassment. Where we think that SH is caused by women being outnumbered by men in workplace is the one of the root causes of this dilemma. From the inception till now, the nature of such cases has changed, the outcomes have changed, and the factors have changed. Dekker and Barling (1998) have concluded that considerable progress has been made against this occupational health problem. Even though we have seen a decrease in complaints by 25.8%, there has been a rise of males filing complaints by a 15.3%. This complexity in the treatment of SH is a result of two factors. First, the stereotypical view of sexual harassment as a "woman's problem" and an increased number of emerging gays, transgender and lesbian workforce members. The study suggested that since SH is a case of intentionality, it cannot be predicted. However, there can be preventable actions against it; implementation of consequential sanctions backed by firm policies can be a fruitful measure of prevention.

III. Methodology

Research Design

A quantitative research style is being adopted for the research in question. This research style is one of the most common methods of conducting research or analysis on a particular topic. This style allows data to be analyzed in numerical form.

Research Paradigm

Research paradigm can be defined as the mutual agreement between scientists or scholars about how a particular problem has to be addressed or solved (Kuhn, 1962) .The research for this particular study, paradigm will be POSITIVISM. This means that there is no single truth and reality for the research in question. However, it can be measures and quantified using various tools such as a questionnaire.

Data Analysis method

SPSS software will be used to run the data. Data will be fed into the statistical software in order to analyze results and further recommendations will be provided accordingly. Questionnaire has been used to collect data and several tests will be run which include descriptive, reliability analysis, regression, and correlation.

Sampling method and size

Data from this research has been collected using a convenient sampling method and the sample size of 180 people was chosen to fill in the questionnaire that was distributed online.

Sample Size Justification

There is no scholarly consensus of ideal sample size on this topic. Other similar studies such as that of Anwar, Osterman and Bjorkqvist (2019) collected data through questionnaire from around 500 females and Buchanan et al. (2018) sample size was around 129 people collected from the corporate world. However, this research is collecting data from 180 employees from various corporations in Karachi, Pakistan. This sample size is justified by research conducted by Fritz and MacKinnon (2007,p12) stating that the appropriate sample size is around 183 for analysis that included one mediating variable.

Hypothesis Statement

H1: SH at workplace negatively influences Job Performance.

H2: SH at workplace negatively influences well-being of employees.

H3: Gender ratio moderates the influence of SH on task performance, job performance and mental health.

Method of research

SEM (Structural equation modeling)

Measures

The online questionnaire included measures of sexual harassment, well-being of employees, job performance, task performance and gender ratio acting as a mediating variable. Likert scale was used from 1 to 5 where 1 was strongly dissatisfied and 5 were strongly satisfied. The items were coded appropriately as per requirement of SPSS software.

IV. Data Analysis

Respondent Profile

Demographic items	Frequency	Percentile
Gender Ratio		
All men	2	2.5%
Majority Men	41	51.2%
Equal ratio	31	38.8%
Majority Women	6	7.5%
All women	0	0
Age		
15-25	30	37.5%
26-35	50	62.5%
36-45	0	0
46-55	0	0
56-65	0	0

Sexual Harassment, Mental Health & Job-Related Outcomes: A Case from

An online questionnaire was drafted to collect responses from various private sector organizations in Pakistan and 80 responses were recorded altogether. The results of the potential respondents are summarized in the table above. It is evident from the table that majority organizations in Pakistan are dominated majorly by men (51.2%) or they have an almost equal ratio of both men and women (38.8%).

Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	Std.Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
Sexual Harassment	17.49	6.794	1.998	4.495
Well being	43.40	11.687	-.376	-.947
Job Performance	6.36	2.002	-.157	-.656
Task Performance	9.96	2.918	-.222	-.733
Gender Ratio	2.51	.675	.460	-.194

The above table shows a summary of descriptive statistics of all the variables being studied. According to the table, Sexual harassment has the highest-level Skewness (Mean 17.49). While on the other hand, the weakest Skewness is that of job performance with a negative value of -.157 (Mean, 6.36). Similarly, the highest Kurtosis value is that of sexual harassment and the lowest is that of gender ratio. However, all values are around ± 3.5 , it is assumed that the data has a normal tendency (Hair Jr. et al, 2010).

4.3. Data Reliability

Variables	No. of items	Chronbach's alpha
SH	11	0.873
WB	14	0.946
JP	2	0.802
TP	3	0.896
Overall	30	0.928

Reliability of the data of the data was tested in order to analyze the consistency of the data collect and Chronbach's alpha is considered to be the most common method that is used to measure the reliability of the instrument used, that is, the questionnaire. Many renowned researchers such as Haier et al. (1998) have highlighted the importance of data reliability and stated that it is an integral part when carrying a quantitative research. The benchmark for a good

Sexual Harassment, Mental Health & Job-Related Outcomes: A Case from

Chronbach's alpha is 0.60 and the values retrieved exceed the given benchmark. This means that the data is reliable and can further be scrutinized and analyzed.

Pearson Correlation

Measures	SH	WB	JP	TP	GR			
SH	Pearson							
	Correlation			1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)							
	N			80				
WB	Pearson							
	Correlation			.083	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)			.465				
	N			80	80			
JP	Pearson							
	Correlation			.024	.737**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)			.832	.000			
	N			80	80	80		
TP	Pearson							
	Correlation			.116	.777**	.728**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)			.306	.000	.000		
	N			80	80	80	80	
GR	Pearson							
	Correlation			.017	.218	.179	.190	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)			.884	.053	.111	.092	
	N			80	80	80	80	80

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Sexual Harassment, Mental Health & Job-Related Outcomes: A Case from

Pearson Correlation is a test that is ran in order to analyze the relationship amongst the variables being scrutinized (Bryman & Bell, 2005). It is further also stated that in order to run the regression test, finding the correlation amongst variables is essential part of the research. The benchmark for correlation states that it should be between 0.20-0.90. If the co-relation for a particular variable is less than 0.20 then it is recommended to drop that variable and if it's greater that 0.90 then the variable should be either dropped or merged with another variable.

According to the results retrieved, wellbeing of employees has a significantly strong relationship with job, task performance as well as with gender ratio. While Sexual harassment is witnessed to have links with all three variables.

Regression Analysis

H1: Sexual Harassment has a negative relationship with Job performance

		Unstandardized		Standardized	
Model 1		Coefficients		Coefficients	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	
1	(Constant)	16.968	2.561		.000
	JP	.082	.384	.024	.832

a. Dependent Variable: SH

The regression results basically highlight the fact that the predictor which is in this case job performance explains 2.4% (Beta) of the variance which is sexual harassment. And that the P value is .832.

H2: Sexual Harassment has a negative relationship with wellbeing of employees

		Unstandardized		Standardized	
Model 2		Coefficients		Coefficients	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	
1	(Constant)	15.399	2.947		.000
	WB	.048	.066	.083	.465

a. Dependent Variable: SH

This denotes that well-being of employees predicts 8.3% of the variant which is sexual harassment and that the significant value is .465 and is not significant enough as denoted by the significance value of .465.

H3: Gender ratio moderates the influence of SH on task performance, job performance and mental health.

Model 3		Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.
		Coefficients		Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	15.113	2.735		5.525	.000
	Moderator	.032	.035	.102	.904	.369

a. Dependent Variable: SH

Third hypothesis suggested that gender ratio acts as a moderator to increase sexual harassment at workplace, this influences task performance, job performance and well-being of employees. Gender ration predicts the variance by 90.4% which is a quite high value.

V. Conclusion and Recommendation

Discussion & Conclusion

The world is going through a phase of globalization; this revolution has caused significant changes in the work force. On one hand the world has encouraged and pushed women to join the work force and began recognizing them. Furthermore, they are denoted as the soul of any nation and without them an economy cannot prosper. The increased participation of women in the workforce is considered as an indicator of development. However, on the other hand the society consists of these ‘culprits’ that mistreat women, which then raises a barrier for them flourish and which inevitable causes an impact upon the economy as a whole. Furthermore, when this kind of harassment and violence is found to be a part of the workplace where people are hired because of their sound educational backgrounds raises questions and brows of all scholars (Sadruddin, 2013). Sexual Harassment is a common practiced behavior or conduct that is witnessed in several workplaces. This is the truth of what are society is like and where this society is going in terms of how women are treated around the world. Furthermore, United Nations has produced a definition of harassment by stating that it is behavior either verbal or physical; that is regarded as offensive and which inevitably get in the way of work. Sexual harassment is considered to be the most common type and which is regarded unethical and threatening to women (Goonesekere, 2004). Sexual harassment basically is unwanted or uncalled for but however remains a strong part of cultures in innumerable organisations and all around the world (Fitzgeralds, Swan, & Magley, 1997). This harassment introduces itself in different forms which include sexual coercion, an act of gaining attention, etc. (Fitzgeld, Gelfand, & Drasgow, 1995).

This study particularly has focused itself on understanding cases of sexual harassment in Pakistan. The society and environment in a country like a Pakistan is unsupportive, uncooperative and extremely difficult for all those women who choose to step out in order to become the bread earner for their respective families (Ali, & Kramer, 2015). Moreover, there are numerous cases found

where working females are victims of harassment and inappropriate behaviors within their workplaces. Female workers either have to fight to get their rights or have to submit to working in hostile environment. The management and their male colleagues provide no encouragement to the females working in their organisations to stand up for themselves and contribute in building the economy. And therefore, sexual harassment needs to be investigated and eradicated (Aasha, 2002).

This research drafted a model where it was analyzed that whether sexual harassment had an impact on task, job performance of employees and whether gender ratio moderated this relationship. The results clearly indicated that the lower proportion of women in organisations triggered sexual harassment and had a strong impact on task and job performance of employees and has a direct impact on the well-being of employees. According to the questionnaire filled by organisations in Pakistan, it was evident that most of the organisations are majorly male dominated and that women

are in lower proportion. Even though there was not a strong relationship of task, work and well-being of employees with sexual harassment, this may be due to the questions asked as they maybe too open for a closed society like Pakistan, as Ali and Kramer (2015) have suggested in their research that females do not feel comfortable discussing these issues openly due to the fear factor or shame.

Recommendations

It is extremely essential to eradicate all forms of sexual harassment from Pakistani organisations and employers and HR managers need to adopt proactive measures in order create a healthy working environment for female staff in an organisation. Furthermore, Ali and Kramer (2015) have stated that training and counselling services should be provided to all female staff in organisations in order to help them learn what to do or how to face a harassment situation. Studies have shown that people in Pakistan are less likely to respond to sexual harassment due to higher power distance cultures and unawareness of where to complain (Merkin, & Shah, 2014). Furthermore, victimizations are another huge issue in Pakistan and that females are not encouraged to take action on being harassed due to poor treatment of the complaint made and inappropriate procedures (Hoque, & Noon, 2004). HR managers need to develop bodies that effectively investigate complains' of harassment cases and take strict measures to avoid retaliation and victimization. None of these policies or procedures is bound to work unless or until guaranteed protection is provided to female employees in organisations.

Bibliography

- [1.] Agarwal and Gupta M (2000) *Sexual Harassment in the Workplace*, 3rd Edition. Vancouver: Butterworths.
- [2.] Ali, F., & Kramer, R. (2015). An exploratory study of sexual harassment in Pakistani organizations. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, 32(1), 229-249.
- [3.] Anwar, F., Österman, K., & Björkqvist, K. (2019). Three types of sexual harassment of females in public places in Pakistan. *Journal of Contemporary Medicine*, 9(1), 65-73.
- [4.] Bernard, J. 1969. *The sex game* London. Leslie Frewin
- [5.] Blumenthal, J. A. (1998). The reasonable woman standard: A meta-analytic review of gender differences in perceptions of sexual harassment. *Law and Human Behavior*
- [6.] Bowman, C. G. (1993). Street harassment and the informal ghettoization of women. *Harvard Law Review*, 106, 517-580.
- [7.] Brislin, R. (2014). *The effective security officer's training manual*. Butterworth-Heinemann.
- [8.] Bryman, A., & Bell, E. (2007). *Business Research Methods*. NY: Oxford University Press. Buchanan, D., & Bryman, A. (2009). *Organizational Research Methods*. SAGE Publication Ltd.
- [9.] Buchanan, N. T., Settles, I. H., Wu, I. H., & Hayashino, D. S. (2018). Sexual harassment, racial harassment, and well-being among Asian American women: An intersectional approach. *Women & Therapy*, 41(3-4), 261-280.
- [10.] Dekker, I., & Barling, J. (1998). Personal and organizational predictors of workplace sexual harassment of women by men. *Journal of occupational health psychology*, 3(1), 7.
- [11.] Fairchild, K., & Rudman, L. A. (2008). Everyday stranger harassment and women's objectification. *Social Justice Research*, 21(3), 338-357.
- [12.] Fitzgerald, L. F. (1993). Sexual harassment: Violence against women in the workplace.
- [13.] *American Psychologist*,
- [14.] Fitzgerald, L. F. (1993). Sexual harassment: Violence against women in the workplace. *American Psychologist*, 48(10)

- [15.] Fitzgerald, L. F., Gelfand, M. J., & Drasgow, F. (1995). Measuring sexual harassment: Theoretical and psychometric advances. *Basic and applied social psychology*, 17(4), 425-445.
- [16.] Fitzgerald, L. F., Swan, S., & Magley, V. J. (1997). But was it really sexual harassment? Legal, behavioral, and psychological definitions of the workplace victimization of women.
- [17.] Fitzgerald. (1988). The incidence and dimensions of sexual harassment in workplace and academia. *Journal of vocational behavior*.
- [18.] Fritz, M. S., & MacKinnon, D. P. (2007). Required sample size to detect the mediated effect.
- [19.] *Psychological science*, 18(3), 233-239.
- [20.] Gardner, C. B. (1995). *Passing by: Gender and public harassment*. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- [21.] Goonesekere, S. (Ed.). (2004). *Violence, law and women's rights in South Asia*. SAGE Publications India.
- [22.] Gutek, B. A. (1985). *Sex and the workplace*. Jossey-Bass Inc Pub.
- [23.] Hadi, A. (2018). Workplace Sexual Harassment and its Underreporting in Pakistan. *European Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 4(1), 148-153.
- [24.] Haier, J. F., Anderson, R. E., Tatham, R. L. & William, C. (1998) *Black 1998, Multivariate data analysis*, 5th ed., (Upper Saddle River).
- [25.] Hair, J., Black, W., Babin, B., & Anderson, R. (2010). *Multivariate data analysis*, Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- [26.] Haspels, N., Zaitum, M., Constance, T., & MacCann, T. (2001). Action against Sexual Harassment at work in Asia and the Pacific Bangkok: ILO Office. Meda, D. 2001. *New Perspectives on work as Value Loutfi PM Eds*. Geneva: International Labour Office, 21-32.
- [27.] Hoque, K., & Noon, M. 2004. Equal opportunities policy and practice in Britain: Evaluating the 'empty shell' hypothesis. *Work, Employment & Society*, 18: 481-506.
- [28.] Ilies, R., Hauserman, N., Schwochau, S., & Stibal, J. (2003). Reported incidence rates of work-related sexual harassment in the United States: using meta-analysis to explain reported rate disparities. *Personnel Psychology*, 56(3), 607-631.
- [29.] Johnson, C. B., Stockdale, M. S., & Saal, F. E. (1991). Persistence of men's misperceptions of friendly cues across a variety of interpersonal encounters. *Psychology of Women Quarterly*, 15(3), 463-475.
- [30.] Kinsey, A. C., Martin, C. E., & Pomeroy, W. B. (1948). *Sexual Behavior in the Human Male*:
- [31.] Alfred C. Kinsey... Wardell B. Pomeroy... Clyde E. Martin. WB Saunders C°.
- [32.] Lahsaeizadeh, A., & Yousefinejad, E. (2012). Social aspects of women's experiences of sexual harassment in public places in Iran. *Sexuality & Culture*, 16(1), 17-37.
- [33.] Logan, L. (2015). Street harassment: Current and promising avenues for researchers and activists. *Sociology Compass*, 9, 96-211.
- [34.] Louise F. Fitzgerald, M. J. (2010). *Measuring Sexual Harassment: Theoretical and Psychometric Advances*. Basic and applied psychology.
- [35.] Madge, C. (1997). Public parks and the geography of fear. *Tijdschrift voor economische en sociale geografie*, 88(3), 237-250.
- [36.] Magley, V. J., Waldo, C. R., Drasgow, F., & Fitzgerald, L. F. (1999). The impact of sexual harassment on military personnel: Is it the same for men and women?. *Military Psychology*, 11(3), 283-302.
- [37.] McDonald, P., & Charlesworth, S. (2016). Workplace sexual harassment at the margins. *Work, employment and society*, 30(1), 118-134.

Sexual Harassment, Mental Health & Job-Related Outcomes: A Case from

[38.] Merkin, R. S., & Shah, M. K. (2014). The impact of sexual harassment on job satisfaction, turnover intentions, and absenteeism: findings from Pakistan compared to the United States. *SpringerPlus*, 3(1), 215.

[39.] Millet, Kate. "Sexual politics (nueva York." (1970).

[40.] Pain, R. (1991). Space, sexual violence and social control: Integrating geographical and feminist analyses of women's fear of crime. *Progress in human geography*, 15(4), 415-431.

[41.] Pina, A., Gannon, T. A., & Saunders, B. (2009). An overview of the literature on sexual harassment: Perpetrator, theory, and treatment issues. *Aggression and violent behavior*, 14(2), 126-138.

[42.] Quick, J. C., & McFadyen, M. (2017). Sexual harassment: Have we made any progress?. *Journal of occupational health psychology*, 22(3), 286.

[43.] Sadruddin, M. M. (2013). Sexual harassment at workplace in Pakistan-Issues and remedies about the global issue at managerial sector.

[44.] SIEGEL, R. B. (2003). A Short History of Sexual Harassment . CATHAIUNE A MACKINNON & REVA B. SIEGEL EDS. FORTHCOMING YALE PRESS .

[45.] Stanko, E. A. (1995). Women, crime, and fear. *The Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 539(1), 46-58.

[46.] Stockdale, M. S. (1993). The Role of sexual misperceptions of women' s friendliness in an emerging theory of sexual harassment. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 42(1), 84-101.

[47.] Syed, J., Ali, F., & Winstanley, D. (2005). In pursuit of modesty: Contextual emotional labour and the dilemma for working women in Islamic societies. *International Journal of Work Organisation and Emotion*, 1(2), 150-167.

[48.] Tangri, S. S., Burt, M. R., & Johnson, L. B. (1982). Sexual harassment at work: Three explanatory models. *Journal of social Issues*, 38(4), 33-54.

[49.] Taylor, V. V. (1985). United States Court of Appeals, District of Columbia Circuit.

[50.] Walby, S. (1990). *Theorizing patriarchy*. Basil Blackwell.

[51.] Wilder, R. A. (2018). *Sexual Harassment, Public Transportation, and Labor Market Outcomes for Women: Case Study of Lahore, Pakistan*.

Appendix

STATEMENTS	15-25	25-35	35-45	45-55	55-65
Age	1	2	3	4	5

STATEMENTS	All men	Majority men	Equal ratio	Majority women	All women
Gender ratio in your organization	1	2	3	4	5

STATEMENTS	Not sure	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often
Manager/Coworker made sexual comments, jokes, gestures, or looks	1	2	3	4	5
Manager/Coworker showed, gave, or left sexual pictures, photographs, messages, or notes	1	2	3	4	5
Manager/Coworker pulled your clothing off or down	1	2	3	4	5
Manager/Coworker wrote sexual messages/graffiti about you on bathroom walls, etc.	1	2	3	4	5
Manager/Coworker spread sexual rumors about you	1	2	3	4	5

Manager/Coworker said they were gay or lesbian	1	2	3	4	5
Manager/Coworker Touched, grabbed, or pinched you in a sexual way	1	2	3	4	5
Manager/Coworker Blocked your way a sexual way	1	2	3	4	5
Manager/Coworker Forced to kiss you	1	2	3	4	5
Manager/Coworker Forced you to do something sexual, other than kissing	1	2	3	4	5
Manager/Coworker touched your private parts when you did not want to	1	2	3	4	5

Bullying Perpetration and Subsequent Sexual Violence Perpetration Among Middle School

Students, Department of Educational Psychology, University of Illinois, Champaign, Illinois

Sexual Harassment, Mental Health & Job-Related Outcomes: A Case from

STATEMENTS	None of the time	Rarely	Some of the time	Often	All of the time
I have been feeling optimistic about the future	1	2	3	4	5
I've been feeling useful	1	2	3	4	5
I've been feeling relaxed	1	2	3	4	5
I've been feeling interested in other people	1	2	3	4	5
I've had energy to spare	1	2	3	4	5
I've been dealing with problems well	1	2	3	4	5
I've been thinking clearly	1	2	3	4	5
I've been feeling good about myself	1	2	3	4	5
I've been feeling close to other people	1	2	3	4	5
I've been feeling confident	1	2	3	4	5
I've been able to make up my own mind about things	1	2	3	4	5
I've been feeling loved	1	2	3	4	5
I've been interested in new things	1	2	3	4	5
I've been feeling cheerful	1	2	3	4	5

Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-being Scale (WEMWBS) © NHS Health Scotland, University of Warwick and University of Edinburgh

STATEMENTS	Strongly disagree	Rarely	Some of the time	Often	Strongly agree
I like my job better than the average worker does	1	2	3	4	5
most days I am enthusiastic about my job	1	2	3	4	5
I find real enjoyment in my job	1	2	3	4	5

Job Stress, Job Involvement, Job Satisfaction, and Organizational Commitment and Their Associations with Job Burnout Among Indian Police Officers, Society for Police and Criminal Psychology 2017

STATEMENTS	None of the time	Rarely	Some of the time	Often	All of the time
Task performance					
I managed to plan my work so that it was done on time	1	2	3	4	5
My planning was optimal	1	2	3	4	5
I kept in mind the results that I had to achieve in my work	1	2	3	4	5
I was able to separate main issues from side issues at work	1	2	3	4	5
I was able to perform my work well with minimal time and effort.	1	2	3	4	5
Contextual performance					
I took on extra responsibilities.	1	2	3	4	5
I started new tasks myself, when my old ones were finished	1	2	3	4	5
I took on challenging work tasks, when available.	1	2	3	4	5
I worked at keeping my job knowledge up-to-date	1	2	3	4	5
I worked at keeping my job skills up-to-date.	1	2	3	4	5

I came up with creative solutions to new problems.	1	2	3	4	5
Counterproductive work behavior					
I complained about unimportant matters at work.	1	2	3	4	5
I made problems greater than they were at work.	1	2	3	4	5
I focused on the negative aspects of a work situation, instead of on the positive aspects.	1	2	3	4	5
I spoke with colleagues about the negative aspects of my work.	1	2	3	4	5
I spoke with people from outside the	1	2	3	4	5

organization about the negative aspects of my work.					

Construct Validity of the Individual Work Performance Questionnaire

Linda Koopmans, MSc, Claire M. Bernaards, PhD, Vincent H. Hildebrandt, PhD, Henrica C. W. de Vet, PhD, and Allard J. van der Beek, PhD